

XORIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

DEFINITION CONCEPT REVEALING THE MEANING OF CONSTRUCTION TERMINOLOGY FROM ENGLISH TO UZBEK BASED ON DEFINITION CONCEPT

Ostonova Ramziya

Uzbekistan State World Languages University (Phd student)

astonovaramziya@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15179472>

Annotation: *This thesis had shed light on defining definition concept as well as applying it to construction term system. Some examples are providing in order to clarify the usage of definition concept. This concept can be deployed not only architecture and construction domain, but also term-related field.*

Keywords: *definition concept, construction terminology, term, term system.*

Introduction. Architectural styles, motifs and elements are often deeply tied to the culture and history of a region. Translating these terms requires not only linguistic expertise but also a cultural understanding to capture nuanced connotations and references. For example, the translation of terms related to traditional architecture. Russian terminologist N.S. Sharafutdinova argues that the distinguishing feature of terms from other lexical compounds is the need for a definition that providing definition. The definition serves to determine the meaning of the term. When in use, the term is replaced by the desired explanation or **definition**. The explanation or definition of science and technology is illuminated by its logical rigidity, completeness, a clarity and detailed explanation or description of all the features and limits of scientific and technical concept. The volume of the definition of the terms is, as a rule, a couple of lines. This is called the concept of definition, which allows the sphere to express the concepts of the field and distinguish it from other units (Sharafutdinova N.S, 2016).

Another mentioning features of the terms, according to Abdurahmanova A.Z., is their need for definition and **interpretation**. The definition serves to determine the meaning of the term. For this reason, the term is sometimes used with an explanation or definition This concept of explanation or definition helps to distinguish all the concepts of the field. If we apply “definition” concept on revealing the meaning or translating construction terminology. It contribute to provide brief image about any notion. By taking example from construction terminology it is attempted to reveal the meaning of terms from English to Uzbek based on “definition” concept.

ANGLE FLOAT-ikki qirrali burchakka ega bo'lgan kurakcha,yangi quyilgan betonni tekislash uchun ishlatilindi-Andava.

XORIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

AWNING- Soya qiluvchi qoplama-Naves

BASEBOARD, mopboard, scrubboard-uy devorlarining pastki qismiga biriktiriladigan uzun taxta, chaspak.

FRENCH ROOF-ba'zan mansard shaklida ham qo'llaniladi, Fransuz uslubidagi tom, Fransuz tomi, tomonlari perpendikulyar shakldagi tom.

FRENCH WINDOW-Fransuz uslubidagi deraza, Fransuzcha deraza. Polgacha kengaytirilgan deraza.

ITALIANATE HOUSE OR VILLA-Italyan uslubidagi uy shaklida ham ishlatiladi, ikki qavatli, chordoqqa ham ega, bu turdagi uylar Shimoliy Italiyada urf bo'lib badavlat fermerlar va feodallarning uyi bo'lgan.

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

For terms with complex cultural or historical connotations, providing definitions or description can help the target audiences better understand the significance of the term. Construction terms can be tied to specific historical periods or events. When translating such terms, it is crucial to retain the historical context. For instance, terms related to ancient architectural styles or landmarks might require additional explanations to help the target audience understand their historical significance. Also, using visual aids, diagrams, illustrations, photographs, or 3D models to supplement translated text can help bridge language barriers and provide a clear understanding of architectural elements, styles and concepts. Including images, diagrams or examples of the architectural elements being discussed can enhance the understanding of the translated terms. Visual aids provide a visual presentation of the cultural and historical context. A direct translation might not capture the same cultural and historical nuances, so the translators need to consider equivalent terms or “**definition concept**” that resonate with target culture. Translating architectural terms from historical periods can be particularly challenging. Not only do these terms carry specific historical contexts, but they might also refer to construction techniques and materials that are no longer in use. *Maintaining the historical accuracy while making the concepts understandable to modern readers can be effective solution together with supporting definition contributes to reveal the meaning and context as clear as glass.*

References:

1. Шарафутдинова Н.С. О понятиях «Терминология», «Терминосистема» и «Терминополе» // Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики. 2016. – №6-3 (60). – С. 168 –171.
2. Абдурахманова Алие Заировна Лингвистическое моделирование строительной терминологии (на материале английского языка) Специальность 10.02.21 – Прикладная и математическая лингвистика Диссертация на соискание ученой степени кандидата филологических наук Москва 2016.
3. Dictionary of architecture and Construction fourth edition by Cyril M. Harris.2006\2300 illustrations.